

Opportunities and Challenges of Labor based Participatory Approach in Road Construction in Nepal: A Case Study of District Road Support Program funded road projects, Ramechhap, Nepal

Anjay Kumar Mishra, Bijaya Rana Magar

Abstract— the overall objective of this study is to assess the opportunities and challenges of Labor based Participatory Approach in road construction in Nepal. Primary data were collected through questionnaire survey and interviews where secondary data were collected from publications and progress reports of District Coordination Committee (DCC), Ramechhap. The results showed that 72631 man-days were involved in Financial Year (FY) 2010/11 for four road constructions and number was increased by 421863 in FY 2012/13. At the end of Phase IV (FY 2013/14), in total 790172 man-days were involved in construction which means high level of employment generation. NRs. 681515657 was spent in Phase IV and most of amount went to workers' hand in cash. 78% respondents were satisfied in their income whereas 23 households started new business after project. Projects really helped to improve their financial and livelihood condition. 72% respondents felt that these roads are their own asset and should be protected. It shows that community people have felt ownership in some extent and projects could be sustained as expectation. It was also found that quality of materials and works were controlled by User Committees better than contractors. Public Hearing Program, cash distribution to labors in site/community showed the transparency of project. Involvement of 17077 workers from Disadvantage Group (DAG) and 6015 female workers in Phase IV showed example of gender equity and social inclusion. As challenges, NRs. 681515657 in four financial year for construction, upgrade/rehabilitation of 65km road was found expensive and time consumed. It was found that sometimes conflicts were raised between stakeholders and in user committees mainly about contingencies and management cost. 73% of respondents felt fear about accident and 56% were found confused and doubt about safety measures, i.e., lack of confidence about safety. It was found that though there are many challenges, but Labor based Participatory Approach brings several opportunities in district. As recommendation, stakeholders should be oriented from first day about their responsibilities and facilities. Road workers should be oriented and motivated about safety equipment/measures and insurances from first day of works.

Index Terms— Financial Year, livelihood, ownership, Public Hearing Program, conflict, safety measures

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Participatory Approach is one of the important and frequently used approaches for planning and implementing projects in Nepal [1]. Local Self Governance Act, 1999 (LSGA) and Local Self Governance Rules, 2000 (LSGR) have given provisions for Participatory and Bottom Up Approach in planning and implementation [2]. District Road Support Program (DRSP), under Government of Nepal (GoN) and Swiss Development Cooperation (SDC) as donor agency, has been implemented various road projects adopting Labor based Participatory Approach in Nepal. DRSP was implemented as Phase I from Financial Year 2000/01 to 2002/03 in Ramechhap

District, Nepal. It was continued as Phase II from 2003/04 to 2005/06, Phase III from 2006/07 to 2009/10 and ended as Phase IV from 2010/11 to 2013/14. In Phase IV, DRSP took four connectivity in district having total length of 65 km where 34.6 km stone pitching, 1 km gravelling, 13 km cobbling (a swiss technology) were done and 16.4 km road was left as earthen condition [3].

The roads were chosen by stakeholders conducting various meetings in District Coordination Committee (DCC), Ramechhap (Former District Development Committee) and approved from District Council [4]. Roads and road structures were constructed almost by human workmanship using simple tools (chisel, hammer, and crowbar). Thousands of road workers coming from

surrounding villages/communities of district were involved in road construction. The constructions were managed by Project Manager and User Committees and coordinated by DCC, Ramechhap and District Road Coordination Committee (DRCC), Ramechhap [5].

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Stakeholders, beneficiaries and DCC, Ramechhap gravated various opportunities and benefits from this approach. The livelihood of the beneficiaries was improved whereas the spirits of ownership and sustainability were established.

In the other hand, they were faced various construction challenges. They were survived from cost, time and other difficulties.

1.3 Research Objectives

The overall objective of the study is to assess the opportunities and challenges of Labor based Participatory Approach in road construction in Nepal.

1.4 Limitation of the Study:

For questionnaire surveys and interviews of beneficiaries, who were directly involved as workers in road construction, only 100 people from 40 household were taken randomly (without calculating sample size from formulae) as sample and results were assumed to represent the results of population of workers/beneficiaries. Likewise, only roads of Phase IV were taken for the research and results were assumed to represent the other phases of construction.

2 METHODOLOGY

This chapter discusses the methodology used in this research. Research problems were identified and research objectives were set based on problems.

2.1 Study Area

The research was focused in DRSP (Phase IV) supported roads of Ramechhap district, Nepal where the roads were newly constructed, upgraded and rehabilitated. Data were collected from District Coordination Committee (DCC), Ramechhap, representatives of District Road Coordination Committee (DRCC), Ramechhap, Engineers of Department of Roads and involved workers (note: they were also identified as beneficiaries) of the roads. The details of the roads are as follows:

Name of Road	Total length (km)	Population served	Earthen	Stone Pitching	Cobbling	Graveling
Khimti Namadi Betali Road	34	41937	7.9	25.1	1	0
Pharpu Basey link Road	5	2098	4.5	0.5	0	0
Dharapani Thosey Singati Road	16	13407	4	8.5	3.5	0
Those Chuchure Garjyang Road	10	10682	0	0.5	8.5	1

2.2 Data Collection

Primary data were collected through questionnaire survey and interviews. Mixed types of questions were used to gather information from the respondents. Both formal and informal interviews were taken.

Secondary data were collected from various reports of DCC Ramechhap.

2.3 Data Processing and Analysis

The processing was carried out comprising editing, classifying and tabulation of collected data for easy analysis. The quantitative data from surveys and interviews were entered in Microsoft Excel. Respondents were analyzed in percentage. Qualitative information were analyzed in logical way.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This part consists of results and discussion after processing and analyzing the data which were obtained from primary and secondary sources.

3.1 Opportunities of Approach

Research was found that stakeholders have achieved various opportunities from Labor based Participatory Approach. The opportunities are described as follows:

3.1.1 Employment Generation

Secondary data were collected from DCC, Ramechhap and analyzed. It was found that 72631 man-days were involved in FY 2010/11 to construct those four roads where this number was increased by 421863 in FY 2012/13. It was also found that that until end of Phase IV, there were involvement of 790172 man-days in road constructions.

This result shows that there was adequate level of employment generation from the initial stage of Phase IV. But while reaching until FY 2012/13,

hundreds of road workers were increased into thousands, i.e. high employment generation due to these projects. From the interview with Site Engineer, it was revealed that this increment was due to high volume of excavation and upgrade works in various sections and addition of road structures.

3.1.2 Financial and Livelihood Improvement

After analyzing bills of contract and progress report, it was found that NRs. 681515657 was spent in Phase IV. Except some amount in tool procurement and management amount (around 2% of total payable amount) for User Committees, all ransoms were paid to the workers. After interviewing Site Engineer, it was found that all workers were paid in site with hand cash according to their work book.

Questionnaire survey between 100 workers also revealed that 78% of them were satisfied about their income from the road construction where 2% were found dissatisfied. After interview, it was found that among 40 households, 23 families started new business instead of going abroad, traditional agriculture and being unemployment. It was found that they started small shop, small hotels, cash crop production, and animal farming from earned money and nowadays they can be able to send their children in boarding schools.

This result shows that millions of rupees have directly gone to the workers' hand in cash which really helps to improve their financial conditions. It also shows that mostly workers were satisfied about their income from road construction, as a result, they became capable to establish new business after project and capable to improve their financial situation and family status.

3.1.3 Ownership and Sustainability

Questionnaire survey between 100 workers showed 72% of them feel that these roads are their own asset and should be protected from community where 16% feel that DCC, Ramechhap should take care about it and 12% of them do not know about it. After interviewing Project Manager, Site Engineer and Program Officers of DCC, Ramechhap, it was found that while occurring any adverse condition (landslide, gabion wall displacement) in road sections, firstly they clear the obstacles or protect the road structures temporarily for vehicle movement and immediately inform to DCC, Ramechhap for maintenance. They have restricted heavy loaded vehicles to enter in roads to prevent from road degradation. Community people themselves clean the side drain, maintain the stone pitching and conduct bio engineering works.

These results show that community people have felt ownership in some extent on road projects and projects could be sustained as expectation if these feelings remained continuous in community.

3.1.4 Quality Control

After interviews, it was found that in early stage of Phase IV, DRSP decided to construct some road sections through contractors and they were procured also. The procured contractors in Khimti-Namadi-Betali Road Construction (Shiva-Parbati-Bramhayani J/V and Sunkoshi Construction) failed to perform quality construction as per contract. According to interviews, they wanted to finish the job as fast as possible, as a result, side drains and

stone pitching were damaged during construction phase. Conflicts were raised between these two parties about the construction quality and project faced time overrun. DRSP finished these sections through the contractors penalizing them.

In the other hand, Local Road User Committee (LRUC) also performed same job under direct supervision of technical staffs of DRSP. Road workers were broken down into small groups for several sections, trained for stone pitching and side drain works, oriented about ownership and spreaded in construction sites. According to Project Manager and Site Engineer, the level of performance was found high than performance of contractors. The used materials for stone pitching and side drain were found high quality, the percentage of damages were found very low rather than contractors and improved immediately if required in site as per site technicians' instructions and there were very few conflicts during implementation between DRSP and LRUC.

These results show that quality could be assured and controlled if local resources, especially human power, used properly and effectively.

3.1.5 Transparency

Interviews revealed that there was a high level of transparency during implementation of projects. It was found that various options for road projects were selected from stakeholders in district and chosen these four projects after several meetings in DCC, Ramechhap. LRUCs were formed after conducting meetings in concerned communities and DCC and approved by DRCC and DCC, Ramechhap. Road workers were chosen giving first priority to the communities from where roads were passed.

It was also found that payment of workers were made as per their performances. Quantity of works finished by each worker were measured by site technicians and recorded in their work book. Payments of workers were distributed cash in hand direct in community/site before representatives of DRSP and DCC, Ramechhap. Information and data regards expenditures were presented by LRUC conducting a Public Hearing Program in communities and communities were approved giving them a big clap.

These results indicate that there is a high level of practice regards transparency in labor based participatory approach in DRSP, Ramechhap.

3.1.6 Presence of Gender Equity and Social Inclusion

From secondary data, it was found that among 25725 workers in Phase IV, 17077 were from Disadvantage Group (DAG) and 6015 were female workers. Female workers were paid NRs. 69958475.22 and DAG workers were paid NRs. 261312494.85 in entire phase.

Description	Financial Year				Phase total
	2010/11	2011/12	2012/13	2013/14	
Total no. of workers	2128	6662	9442	7493	25725
Total no. of female workers	1106	1039	1644	2226	6015
Total no. of workers from DAG	1532	4441	6149	4955	17077
Total payment to female workers (in NRs)		13,898,297.27	25,854,437.57	30,205,740.37	69,958,475.22
Total payment to DAG workers (in NRs)		77,013,481.90	107,973,782.17	76,323,230.79	261,312,494.85

After interviewing DCC, DRCC and LRUC members, it was found that as per agreement and log frame of program, they were always given first priority to DAG and female during selection of workers. While bringing additional workers from surrounding villages, they were courage to employ female and DAG workers. Various orientations were given to them about their position, roles and responsibilities in society to strengthening them. Even in formation of LRUC, people from DAG were given first priority and 33% of total members were chosen from female group with compulsion in treasurer position.

These all results show that approach has performed many good practices for gender equity and social inclusion in projects. Female workers and DAG have got platform to enhance their financial condition as well as position, roles and responsibilities in projects and communities.

3.2 Challenges of Approach

Research was also found that several challenges were raised while adopting Labor based Participatory Approach in implementation. The major challenges are described as follows:

3.2.1 Costly/ Expensive

From bills of expenditure, it was found that Phase IV spent NRs. 681515657 for constructing, upgrading and rehabilitating 65 km roads including stone pitching, cobbling, side drain, gabion, retaining wall, causeway and other road construction. After interviewing Engineers of DoR, it was found that it could take average lump sum amount of NRs. 6000000/km if using capital intensive approach (machine used approach), i.e. project could complete in an average lump sum

amount of NRs. 390000000. During interview, almost all DRCC members accepted that expenditure would be reduced if using machines rather than labors for excavation of roads.

Financial Year	Allocated Budget (NRs)	Expenditure (NRs)
2010/11	35000000	35255130
2011/12	145000000	144514185
2012/13	269000000	269324389
2013/14	231250000	232421953
	680250000	681515657

This result shows that district rate for labors in different works is high than rate for machines and used of manpower only for completion of project made the project costly compared with capital intensive approach.

3.2.2 Long Time Consumed

After interviewing with DDC and DRCC, most of them accepted that consuming four Financial Year (From 2010/11 to 2013/14) for 15km new construction and 50km upgrade/rehabilitation of road is higher than they expected. It was also found that more time was consumed during excavation of rocky section and geologically vulnerable section.

This result shows that labor intensive approach could consume more time in implementation period if implementation goes smoothly without any disturbances (natural calamities).

3.2.3 Conflict in Stakeholders

After interviews, it was found that various conflicts were raised between stakeholders and also in Committee family, mainly about contingencies amount. As per agreement, LRUC could get up to 2% of agreement amount for their logistic support and transportation as per actual cost/bill and this 2% of agreement amount became millions of rupees. It was found that LRUC were claimed this amount several times submitted untruthful bills and several times, it was corrected by DDC/DRSP team with amount reduction. Sometimes DRCC also were shown unnecessary interest about this amount. In User Committee family, some of the members were wanted to misuse this amount and debated with other members and these all pictures were shown during Public Hearing Program.

These results show that the supports, contingency amounts could raise disputes between stakeholders and User Committees if not properly handled and managed. It should be scientifically managed and distributed to reduce conflict.

3.2.4 Perception about Safety Issues

After questionnaire survey, it was found that 73% of them felt fear about accident while working in slopy rocky sections and landslide prone sections. Likewise, 56% of them could not believe totally on safety equipment and measures which they used during construction. Interviews also revealed that workers were discussed with DCC and LRUC several times about consequences and financial burden if something happen though millions of rupees were invested for their insurance during implementation.

These results show that workers feel fear about the accidents, hard to believe about safety measures

though there are adequate and easily handled safety equipment in sites. They doubt about the financial burden if something happen during construction though they all are insured by projects. Hence, projects should also focus on psychological management while implementing labor based approach.

4 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter includes the conclusions and recommendations after assessing opportunities and challenges of Labor based Participatory Approach in road construction in Nepal.

5.1 Conclusions:

Labor based Participatory Approach, adopted by District Road Support Program, Ramechhap, is found effective source of various opportunities. High employments were generated during construction of four donor funded roads named DRSP, Phase IV. Projects have highly contributed for improving financial and livelihood conditions of road workers as well as other beneficiaries of communities. Strong feelings about project ownership has established in stakeholders and communities and hence projects could effectively operate and sustain as expectation. It was also seen

that construction quality could be assured and controlled effectively if properly managed and handled the local user committees, stakeholders and labor groups. The approach was found transparent and strong presence of gender equity and social inclusion.

In the other hand, it was also seen that labor intensive works could be costly and time consumed if mechanical equipment are replaced by only human power. Conflicts and disputes could be generated between stakeholders and in user committee. More than half of road workers were also found fear about accident, confusion and doubt about safety equipment and measures though there were adequate provision and availability of safety equipment and workers' insurance.

5.2 Recommendations:

Based on this study, following recommendations are made:

- ❖ Local Road User Committee should be clearly oriented from the beginning of project about the logistic support, their obligation and responsibility, project's limitation, rights of project team/office for taking action if anything happened.
- ❖ Road workers should be oriented about safety equipment and measures from the beginning of project. They should be motivated about using these measures by giving prizes, incentives, short tours, and picnic and refreshment program if they

follow guidelines about using safety measures.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors wish to thank especially Er. Dilli Adhikari, Site Engineer/Vice Project Manager, DRSP-Phase IV for his valuable information, supports during field visit, questionnaire survey and interviews of stakeholders and secondary data. Authors also like to thank DCC, Ramechhap, for providing progress reports, bills of expenditures, publications and other relevant documents as well as DRCC, Ramechhap, LRUCs and Engineers of DoR for their valuable information.

REFERENCES

- [1] Shrestha, P., 2013. Practices of Participatory Approach in Infrastructure Development of Nepal. The Annapurna Post, Kathmandu
- [2] GoN, 1999. Local Self-Governance Act. Kathmandu: GoN.
- [3] DRSP, Ramechhap, 2015. Annual Project Report. Ramechhap, District Coordination Committee.
- [4] DRSP, Ramechhap, 2010. Project Minute Book. Ramechhap, District Coordination Committee.
- [5] DRSP, Ramechhap, 2012. Note on Project Implementation. Ramechhap, District Coordination Committee